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BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE

Biology and medicinal properties of field species

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Abstract. Despite the long history of medicinal plant collection in Uzbekistan, there is a lack of information on the current state of the natural population of even the most promising medicinal, food, technical and other raw material plants. there is. The analysis of available materials showed the need to organize a wide scientific research program to clarify the current state of natural medicinal plant reserves, to study the rate of population recovery (results) after harvesting raw materials.

Basic words. Flower, vegetation, budding, gross flowering, fruit, raw material, actinomorph, five-membered calyx, gultoji, gultoji leaves, pollinator, area.

Enter. At present, medicinal plants are grown in specialized farms of our country, farmers, foresters, peasants and other types of ownership. However, due to the fact that the technologies of their cultivation and cultivation are not perfectly developed, some problems are being created that need to be solved and developed. Therefore, providing the pharmaceutical industry with high-quality, abundant, low-cost and environmentally friendly raw materials remains one of the urgent tasks.

Research object and methods used We used the methods of Karshibayev and Ponomoryov to study plant biology, the biology of plant growth, development, and flowering.

The result and their analysis. The genus *Hypericum* belongs to the Hypericaceae family. This family includes 47 families and about 950 species. Most of the species of this family are widespread on the earth, their main representatives are trees and shrubs, distributed in tropical climates. A minority are herbaceous plants, and this group also includes the genus *Hupericum*. This category includes 200 to 400 species. There are 51 species of this family in the territory of the

Commonwealth of Nations. In the territory of the Russian Federation, there are three species of this family (*H. hirsutum* L., *H. perforatum* L. and *H. maculatum* Crantz.) and six species in Central Asia (*H. hirsutum* L., *H. perforatum* L., *H. gebleri* L., *H. scabrum* L., *H. elongatum* L., *H. helianthemoids* L.) are found.

The root system of *H. perforatum* is strongly developed. In the underground part, there are many rhizomes, their length is up to 3-15 cm, and their width is up to 3-5 mm, often they penetrate 2-5 cm, sometimes up to 10 cm in soft soils. Up to 3-4 above-ground parts - stems grow from large root stems. A large number of pubic roots are formed on the root stem. In addition to them, more strongly developed arrow roots are formed, which reach a depth of 155-160 cm in the soil.

Three species of the *Hupericum* family are found in Uzbekistan:

H. elongatum Lyedieb. - long field; *N. scabrum* L. - red scab; *N. perforatum* L. - a hole chayot, field.

***H. elongatum* Lyedyeb.** - A long field. Perennial herb. The height is 40-50 cm, the leaves are opposite, 15-20 mm. Changchili is short compared to the petals, it blooms and seeds in July-August. It grows in rocky and soft soils in the mountain zone. The flowers are collected in a shield-shaped or round-egg-shaped inflorescence. Petals are 18-20 mm, longer than pollen. The long field flower blooms in May and June, and bears fruit in July and August. The fruit is an elongated pod.

***H. scabrum* L.** - Perennial herb. Height 20 - 40 cm. The stem and branches are gnarled. The leaves are long - pencil or lanceolate, 10-15 mm. Branches grow from leaf axils. The ball-flowered thyroid flower blooms and seeds in May - July. It grows in rocky and gravelly areas of hills and mountains. It is found in Central Asia, North Africa, Iran, Mongolia, Japan, China and North America.

In Uzbekistan, it grows in the foothills of Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Samarkand, Jizzakh, along streams, in gardens.

***H. perforatum* L.** – A field with holey leaves. This plant naturally can be obtained from 15-20 quintals of dried raw material per hectare in some mountain regions.

H. perforatum is a southern boreal Eurasian species in the Commonwealth of Independent States, and it is quite widespread on Earth. *H. perforatum* is found

in the middle part of Europe, Central and Asia Minor, North Africa, Iran, Mongolia, Japan, China and North America. *H. perforatum* is often widespread in dry, bright areas, it can be found in mountainous areas up to 2300 m, as well as in forest-steppe and forest regions. Its growth area in nature is very small, and it often occupies small areas.

H. perforatum It is a perennial herb, its height reaches 30-100 cm. The stem grows upright, the upper part is branched, cylindrical in shape. The leaves are opposite to each other on the stem, oval and elliptic in shape, on a branchless stem. The leaves have a small amount of shiny black glandular hairs. The flower organs are free actinomorphic, the calyx is five-membered, the corolla is five, the corolla leaves are light yellow in color, there are many pollinators, often their number is up to 50-60 pieces. Based on pollinators, they are united in three sets. The node is egg-shaped and its length reaches 3-5 mm. A large number of flowers are combined into a tuberos inflorescence. The fruit is an elongated ovoid capsule, 6 mm long and 5 mm wide. A large number of seeds are placed in a very small fruit.

In scientific medicine, the flower is used to remove stomach worms, to prevent fever (malaria) and diarrhea. In folk medicine, this plant is used to treat stomach worms and various worms in the stomach.

Medicinal preparations of the field plant (infusion, nastoyka, liquid extract, imanin preparation) in Kyzylpoycha scientific medicine are used for gastrointestinal (colitis, diarrhea), oral cavity (gingivitis, stomatitis) and II and III diseases. used in the treatment of degree burns. In folk medicine, ground organs are used in the treatment of jaundice (decoction).

Conclusion

To sum up, field species in our climate, only one type of open-leaved field is cultivated, the area of the other two species has decreased. Today, we are carrying out scientific research works for the culturalization of the distribution area and biology of these two species.

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ECONOMICAL SCIENCE
Financial support for socially oriented businesses

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Annotation

Social entrepreneurship has been in the spotlight over the last decade and has certainly shown great potential to become the next big thing. Its supporters are pushing an ambitious plan to create jobs, offer training programs and develop local services in areas with severe and long-standing shortages. A social business is a break-even, non-dividend-paying, financially self-sufficient business designed to solve one or more social problems. Social business is a business focused on achieving goals rather than making profits.

Key words: Investments, social business, financial services, social contributions, sectors, market opportunities, financial instruments, financial sustainability

Introduction

Social business is a business aimed at solving social problems. The investments made by investors are aimed solely at contributing to social welfare and not just to make a profit. However, the investor can get his money back after a certain time and cover all the operating expenses of the organization. Although social business can be carried out in any field, sectors such as health, housing, nutrition, education, financial services for the poor and disadvantaged remain priority. Unlike profit-making organizations, success in social business is determined by the size of the impact it can make or the positive change it can make. Moreover, this is not a business aimed at maximizing profits, but the main goal of social entrepreneurs is to improve the standard of living of the population. When starting a business, difficulties arise in achieving set goals, where socially oriented entrepreneurs need financial support.

Socially conscious businesses often use innovative approaches and models to combine their social mission with a sustainable financial model. This may include creating products or services that address specific social needs, attracting investment

from social investors, or using a portion of profits to fund social programs and projects. Socially oriented businesses can take various forms of organization, including social enterprises, cooperatives, non-profit organizations with for-profit activities, and others. An important aspect of such a business is its openness and transparency regarding social goals, and the measurement and reporting of the social impact achieved by the organization. Hence, it requires giving up the corporate mindset because what may start out as a mole can end up becoming a mountain in 5-6 years. The term "social business" is often confused with social entrepreneurship. Both of them are similar in many ways, but at the same time different in other respects. In fact, social business can be called a component of social enterprise or one of the ways in which social enterprise expresses itself. Moreover, a social enterprise can receive funds from people, through grants or from the government, but a social business cannot. Socially oriented business has several advantages that make it attractive to entrepreneurs and society as a whole. One of the main benefits is solving social problems. Socially oriented business is aimed at solving specific social problems and improving society. This allows entrepreneurs to make a positive impact on people's lives and the environment. New Market Opportunities Addressing social issues can open up new market opportunities. Products and services that help solve social problems and socially oriented businesses can fill a niche in such markets. Another important advantage is attracting talent and motivating employees. Many people want to work for organizations that have a social impact and help people. A socially conscious business can attract talented and motivated employees who share their values and mission. Moreover, grants and funding: Many socially oriented enterprises can attract funding in the form of grants or investments from social investors, non-profit organizations or government programs that support social entrepreneurs. Second, partnerships and collaborations: socially oriented businesses may enter into partnerships with other organizations or businesses to jointly solve social problems or offer joint products or services. This can lead to additional revenue and market expansion. In addition, the "Pay-as-you-can" or "Pay-for-service" model: some socially oriented businesses use flexible

pricing policies, where customers can pay an amount corresponding to their capabilities or the value of the social benefit they receive. This allows a business to make its products or services available to a wide audience while generating revenue. And also, innovative business models: socially oriented enterprises can apply innovative business models that combine commercial activities with solving social problems.

Conclusion

The importance of entrepreneurship and innovation also applies to companies that change the way they produce products and services. The latter companies can use innovative practices and entrepreneurship to establish their brand and become market leaders by doing things that create shared value for society and their companies, and also help change practices in their industry over time.

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HISTORICAL SCIENCE

Development of industrial capacity of Khorazm region: reforms and results

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Annotation: This article discusses the attraction of foreign investments to the economy of Khorezm region, reforms in the economic sphere.

Keywords: investment, industry, Khorezm region, export, joint venture, economy.

If we look at the international recognition of reforms in Uzbekistan, which is being renewed rapidly, in the past historically short period, the political position and influence of Uzbekistan in the Central Asian region and the world has increased dramatically. In the world, the spirit of confidence in New Uzbekistan and the principles of striving for cooperation with the country have increased.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, from the first days of the state administration, in the implementation of the country's foreign policy, set the strengthening of friendly relations and mutually beneficial cooperation with all countries, first of all, with neighboring countries, as a first-level task, and took measures to attract foreign investments and investments to the economy of the country. As a result, during the first five years of the development of New Uzbekistan, a number of activities were carried out to liberalize foreign economic activities and support exports. In particular, the approach to relations with partner countries and international financial institutions has changed radically. Artificial barriers to foreign trade activities were removed, and the export procedure was introduced without advance payments and without guarantee obligations. Also, at a completely new stage of Uzbekistan's development -

On the basis of the priorities defined in the Action Strategy, a new economic policy has been consistently implemented, which is to rapidly develop the industry by attracting foreign investments, which is an important factor for the rapid development of the country, and to expand the share of the industry in the gross domestic product.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoev, on November 11, 2016, at the pre-election meeting held in the Shavot district, outlined specific plans for the modernization of the economy of the Khorezm region as well as for the further development of agriculture, textiles, medicine, tourism, art and other areas. Practical work on the implementation of these issues was started in the region, and significant positive changes were achieved in a short period of time. Investment funds totaling 1 trillion 600 billion soums were attracted to all sectors of the region for two years from all sources.

Indeed, at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the adoption of the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" initiated the period of fundamental democratic reforms and transformational changes in Uzbekistan. In 2017 itself, 11 programs for the development of the republic's territories, as well as 36 programs for the development of individual districts and cities, were adopted.

During the implementation of priority tasks set by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan during his visits to the region in 2017, 2018, the investment attractiveness of the region and the inflow of foreign investment accelerated. In particular, in 2018, the delegation of the Khorezm region visited Belarus, China, Turkey, Turkmenistan and the Russian Federation in order to attract foreign direct investment and develop trade and economic relations. As a result, agreements on the implementation of investment projects with a total value of 181 million US dollars, export contracts worth 62 million US dollars were signed.

Also, it was agreed with the United Arab Emirates company "Armada Group" to attract investments of 100 million dollars to build a tourist complex around "Govukkol", and with the Saudi Arabian company "Ajlan and Bros Holding" on the organization of textile clusters and the implementation of hotel projects. achievement served to further develop the investment potential of the region.

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Possibilities of scanning the historical object "juma mosque".

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Abstract: There are about 60 historical buildings of “Itchan Kala” complex in Khiva. All of them are special and unique. Juma Mosque is one of such historical monuments and this article contains background information of this place.

Keywords: “Juma mosque”, worship destination, carved columns, 3D digitization, conservation, popularization.

Introduction

For the being time the works carried out on the protection of tangible and intangible cultural heritage objects of our country is of great importance. It can be said that the decision of the President on December 19, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of protection of tangible cultural heritage objects" has started a new stage in this regard. Based on paragraph 10 of the decision, it was determined that the territories of the republic included in the UNESCO World Heritage List due to their historical and cultural value are considered to be specially protected historical and cultural territories. A procedure was established for implementation of the construction and improvement projects planned in them in mandatory coordination with the Department of Cultural Heritage and the UNESCO World Heritage Center. Also, Chapter VI of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Protection and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects" defines a number of norms related to the specially protected historical and cultural areas. In 2021-2022, the "roadmap" for the protection of tangible cultural heritage objects, the development of museum activities, and the digitization of the field includes the target indicators of re-historical-cultural examination of real estate objects of tangible cultural heritage in 2021-2022, and the development of their digitized passport and catalog.

The "3D digital Silk Road" is a project that compatible with the policy of digitalization of historical and cultural monuments in Uzbekistan and will be the basis for the digital history of the “Juma Mosque” in Khiva. The view of this

wonderful place is preserved in the virtual world. The historic mosque, which is undergoing constant changes, will have the opportunity to be restored.

Methodolody and materials

“Juma Mosque” is located on the side of the main street surrounding the eastern and western gates of "Itchan Kala". It was one of the prominent buildings of the city in the Middle Ages, and with its unique construction and size, it reminds of the old mosques of Khorezm. It is mentioned for the first time in the works of al-Maqsidi and al-Istahri, Arab travelers who came to Khorezm in the 10th century. Historians, relying on Maqdisi, determine its chronological limit with the 10th century. Some oral information that has come down to us says that the old mosque was demolished and the current mosque was built in its place in 1788 with the same plan and much expanded.

It is known from the historical data that the mosque was rebuilt in 1788 by Abdurahim Boy, the eldest son of Abdurahman Mehtar. Abdurahman Mehtar was buried in a small mausoleum on the east side of the mosque. On the carved door on the southern facade, it is written: "In 1788-89, the mosque was repaired under the leadership of a person named Abdurahman Mekhtar." The exterior of the mosque building is very simple, its height is 4.5 meters, and the height of the minaret is 42 meters. It is a one-story building with a flat roof and there are entrance doors on all four sides and its main entrance is a double-sided gate facing north. The following hadith is written on the panels of this gate in Arabic and suls script: "The best of deeds is a savior, and the best of wealth is a savior." On the walls of the altar on both sides of the altar there are carved letters, one of the letters is dated Hijri 1203 (1788-89) the property and funds of the mosque. The foundation document drawn up in connection with the donation, and the second is information about the history of the mosque written in 1666.

The inner area of the mosque is 55x45 meters and about five thousand people could pray in it. 12 of the 213 ancient decorative columns are preserved here, 8 columns are kept in the “Museum of the History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan” in Tashkent. 108 of the columns were bought from the population in 1983. The initial renovation

of this rare monument began in 1979 based on the project of architect Sonechkin. At this time, it was replaced by decorated columns of the XVIII-XX centuries. In 1996-1997, the Juma Mosque was once again renovated and most of the pillars were replaced.

Scientific results of the work

While researching the history of Juma Mosque, its scientific results were as follows.

- Articles on “Juma Mosque” were published in local magazines (2, 1 in the materials of the conference of HEI, 1 in “Khorezm Haqiqati” newspaper)
- A departmental seminar was held on the subject of syncretization of patterns and inscriptions on the columns of the "Juma Mosque" (historical information written on the columns of the X-XII centuries and hadiths written on the columns of the XV-XVI centuries).

Practical results of the work

The historical appearance of Juma Masjid was captured in the pictures [1] (Fig. 1a), Some of these columns are the oldest monuments of the art of wood carving in all of Uzbekistan. Their replacement and disappearance from year to year seriously damages its history. Therefore, it was supported to be scanned by the team of the "3D digital Silk Road" project [2] (Fig. 1b), Recommendations were made to the relevant organizations to restore the imam's climbing stairs and tomb in the mosque to their old condition. [3] (Fig. 1c).

Fig. 1.: a) Exterior view of Juma Mosque, b) Mosque pillars, c) The climbing ladder of imam in the mosque a tomb

Presidential Decree No. PQ-5150 dated 19.06.2021 "On the organization of activities of the Cultural Heritage Agency under the Ministry of Tourism and Sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for innovative development of the sector" was adopted

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA), grant number PPI/APM/2019/1/00004.

Conclusions

In conclusion, "Juma Mosque" is one of the oldest and unique places of worship in the Islamic world. Today, although Muslims do not practice "Islam" here, it is preserved as a unique historical monument of Khiva. The columns in the "Juma Mosque" are standing the test of time (due to restoration). 3D scanning it and presenting the digitized Juma Masjid to the general public will increase the value of the Masjid and make it known to a large number of people through the Internet.

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MEDICAL SCIENCE

The role of regulatory cytokines in gastrointestinal forms of food allergies in children

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Annotation: Allergic diseases currently occupy a leading place among the most common chronic pathology in childhood. Food allergy is considered today as a multifactorial pathology, in the occurrence and development of which a number of both genetic and environmental factors play a role.

The increase in the prevalence, severity of clinical manifestations of food allergy, the possibility of forming oral tolerance to food products stimulated research on the pathogenesis of the disease and the search for mechanisms to prevent food allergies in children.

The goal of the planned study is to: determine the values of regulatory cytokines TGF β 1 and interleukin 10 in gastrointestinal forms of food allergies in children.

Keywords: food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome, regulatory cytokines, TGF- β 1, Il-10, Ig E.

Materials and methods of research. There were 109 patients aged from 3 months to 3 years under observation. Of the examined patients, 72 were diagnosed with food protein-induced enterocolitis syndrome (with FPIES) and 37 with allergic enteropathies (AE). To establish the diagnosis, clinical anamnestic, paraclinical (general blood test, coprology, feces for latent bleeding, total protein), and immunological (Ig E general, Ig E specific to food antigens by ELISA, determination of the lymphokine producing ability of T-lymphocytes to allergens) studies were used.

The results of the study. Of 72 FPIES patients, 46 (63,9%) had elevated Ig E values ($128,3 \pm 30,0$), among patients with AE there were 20 (54,1%), and the average values were $67,1 \pm 19,1$ Cow's milk proteins (100%) were the leading cause of

allergy development in the observed children, monovalent allergy was more often observed in patients with elevated Ig E values. In the subgroup of FPIES with elevated Ig E values, their number was 47,4 %, and in the subgroup of children with low Ig E values in 35% of cases. The Ige values of specific antibodies to cow's milk proteins were clinically significant and amounted to $1,13 \pm 0.4$ units for FPIES and $0,9 \pm 0,1$ for AE. In case of polyvalent allergy, the causes of food allergy in FPIES were most often beef, eggs, chicken, gluten, soy and citrus fruits were less common. With AE, approximately the same sequence was observed, the values of TGF- β 1 were increased in all groups of patients, higher values of TGF- β 1 were found in patients in the subgroup of patients with high values of Ig E, respectively $42,01 \pm 7,5$ what units and 25.4 ± 6.3 pg/ml, $p < 0.05$, with AE, these values were lower and amounted to 33.7 ± 15.4 in the first subgroup of 30.2 ± 2.8 which units at a norm of 0.43 ± 0.2 pg/ml. The values of IL 10 among patients with FPIES had different values depending on the values of Ig E, so in the subgroup of children with FPIES with elevated values of Ig E, they amounted to 42.8 ± 14.2 pg/ml, and with low values of Ig E- 25.4 ± 6.3 pg/ml, with values in the control group 10.7 ± 2.3 pg/ml. Among patients with AE, these figures were 52.4 ± 16.6 pg/ml (with elevated Ig E values) and 15 ± 3.5 pg/ml (with normal Ig E values). The level of tumor necrosis factor α was significantly increased in both forms of the disease, a comparison between them showed that the highest values were noted in the group of patients with the most severe form of the disease: FPIES associated with high values of Ige: 11.2 pg/ml, while the indicators of healthy children were 4.3 ± 0.7 pg/ml. ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion. The data obtained strongly suggests that cytokines of the TGF- β and IL-10 groups in gastrointestinal forms of food allergies perform the functions of regulators of inflammatory reactions. The regularities of the influence of the levels of transforming growth factor β 1, interleukin 10 on the activation of the process in gastrointestinal forms of food allergy, more pronounced in the association of the underlying disease with elevated values of Ig E.

Mortality predictions in elderly patients with acute heart failure in the intensive care unit

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Key words: heart failure, frailty, elderly, senile age, mortality.

Introduction. A number of factors of unfavorable outcome in the acute of chronic heart failure (AHF) have been identified according to research data. The role of geriatric syndromes as predictors of mortality in elderly patients with AHF has not been sufficiently studied. Assessment of the syndrome of senile asthenia as a marker of mortality in patients with AHF in the intensive care unit (ICU) is relevant.

Objective: to evaluate and identify the most significant predictors of mortality and prolonged ICU stay in patients with AHF.

Materials and methods: 107 patients aged 46-95 years with AHF functional class III-IV were included. 4 groups were formed: 1st - 29 people (53.9 ± 4.5 years), middle age (46-60 years); 2nd - 31 people (68.3 ± 5.0 years) elderly (61-74 years); 3rd - 40 people (81.5 ± 4.1 years) old age (75-89 years). 4th - 7 people (92.4 ± 1.4 years) of the age of centenarians (> 90 years). The patients underwent: examination, echocardiography. Geriatric syndromes were assessed using a comprehensive geriatric assessment (CGE) using the Specialized Geriatric Examination program.

Results. The longest duration in ICU was in the old age group- 5.13 ± 1.9 days. Mortality in the ICU on the 1st day was 1.07%, over the whole period - 14%. The most significant independent predictors of mortality in ICU (OR [95% CI]) were terminal stage of CHF ($52.5 [4.62; 1419.34]$, $p < 0.01$), severe frailty with terminal ($32.0 [5.59; 608.84]$, $p < 0.01$), IV functional class NYHA ($10.6 [2.72; 70.31]$, $p < 0.01$). The most significant independent predictors of long-term stay in ICU (OR

[95% CI]) were terminal stage of CHF (3.6 [2.57; 5.38], $p < 0.01$), terminal frailty (2.9 [1, 85; 4.59], $p < 0.01$), severe frailty (2.6 [1.72; 3.97], $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion. Terminal and severe senile asthenia are independent predictors of a 32-fold increase in mortality and an almost 2.9-fold increase in the duration of stay in ICU of elderly and senile patients.

Indication of specific biomarkers in osteonecrosis after covid-19 in military personnel

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Key words: COVID-19, osteonecrosis, biomarkers, procalcitonin, D-dimer, interleukin-6 (IL-6)

Introduction. Osteonecrosis (ON) is a lesion of various parts of the bone of multiple etiology, occurring in response to impaired blood circulation in it and leading to the death of bone marrow and trabecular bone. Such changes can cause the bone surface to collapse. More often, osteonecrosis refers to damage to the subchondral parts of the bone, but ON can affect various parts. Osteonecrosis of the hip, knee joints, jaws and other rarer locations occurs in approximately 20 thousand people per year. It is possible to divide ON by etiology, pathogenesis, or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data, but any such division will be conditional. For example, we can distinguish iatrogenic OH, which is most often represented by bisphosphonate and glucocorticoid OH. Despite the single unifying factor, the localization, pathogenesis, clinical manifestations, patient population and specialists who treat these types of ON are different (Felson D.T. et al., 2019).

Relevance of the topic. Osteonecrosis of the femoral head (aseptic osteonecrosis, avascular osteonecrosis) is a degenerative disease with necrosis (degradation) of bone cells, which accounts for 1,2%-4,7% of all musculoskeletal diseases and 5% of all destructive hip joint diseases. % (Zhang Y., 2014). According to the World Health Organization, more than 1 million patients diagnosed with osteonecrosis worldwide undergo primary endoprosthetic surgery per year. These numbers show how widespread this disease is. Today, the role of laboratory markers in the development of aseptic necrosis (osteonecrosis) has not been sufficiently studied in the existing literature (Griffith J.F., 2021).

Aim of the study. The aim of the study was to study the values of some biomarkers in the development of aseptic osteonecrosis after COVID-19.

Materials and methods. Indicators of certain biomarkers were studied in 20 patients treated with the diagnosis of osteonecrosis after COVID-19 at the military hospital of the border guard troops of the State Security Service.

The patients who were studied were divided into 2 groups: 11 patients diagnosed with 3-rd degree of aseptic osteonecrosis after COVID-19 made up the first group, 9 patients diagnosed with 1-st degree of aseptic osteonecrosis after COVID-19 made up the second group. In the first group there were 15 men, 5 women, age 18-45, average age 32,3 years. In the second group there were 16 men, 4 women, age 19-41, average age 30,53 years.

General clinical, biochemical (alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, total bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase), immunological (ELISA – enzyme immunoassay) - study of interleukin-6, and molecular-genetic (PCR) methods were used in the research work. indicators of inflammation markers were studied (C-reactive protein, ferritin, procalcitonin), thrombosis indicators (activated partial thromboplastin time - APTT, D-dimer, fibrinogen).

Results. Results of the study: lymphopenia and an increase in the value of neutrophils were found in the analysis of peripheral blood in all patients included in the study groups. Anemia was detected in 4 patients (36,3%) in the first group of patients, and in 3 (33,3%) patients in the second group. The relative index of neutrophils to lymphocytes (N/L index) was 3,99 in the first group and 5,87 in the second group.

The value of immunological index interleukin-6 was 34,1 pg/ml in the first group and 21,1 pg/ml in the second group, and a correlation with the disease level was determined.

The inflammation index C-reactive protein was $61,5 \pm 4,24$ mg/l in the first group, and $28,2 \pm 3,18$ mg/l in the second group ($R < 0,05$).

D-dimer was 0,88 mg/ml in the first group and 0,61 mg/ml in the second group, and there was a direct correlation with the amount of C-reactive protein ($R < 0.05$).

Procalcitonin was 0,8 $\mu\text{g/l}$ in the first group and 0,5 $\mu\text{g/l}$ in the second group and showed correlation with the disease level.

In the majority of cases with elevated levels of the above biomarkers, patients were found to have stage 3 osteonecrosis following COVID-19.

Conclusions. Patients with elevated levels of biomarkers D-dimer, C-reactive protein, interleukin-6 and procalcitonin were most often diagnosed with later stages of osteonecrosis after COVID-19. It can be evaluated as indicators that determine the speed of the pathological process.

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE

Processes of physical training of young handball players

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Annotation: This article deals with the activity of movement of handball players in the game and the implementation of technical and tactical processes in the game, as well as the physical qualities of handball players.

Keywords: Handball, game, group, ball, action, physical, technique, tactics, preparation, skill, skill.

Handball is the most popular sport in the world. Today, in the educational institutions of our republic, the sport of handball is included in the curriculum as a science and a means of health. Achieving a high result in these situations related to sharp confrontations requires handball players to show the ability of stable movement along with the qualities of quickness, strength, agility, and endurance.

It has been scientifically proven that accurate, fast and effective performance of technical skills, implementation of tactical combinations to the goal appropriate to the situation is closely related to the physical qualities of each type of sports game. In the studies, it was recommended to group and use many sets of exercises designed to develop physical qualities suitable for certain sports (football, volleyball, handball). In particular, group 1 exercises are performed within the rules of the game. Group 2 - in a situation outside the scope of the rules of the game, group 3 exercises do not end with the final shot or ball throw (handball, basketball) (players only pass the ball to each other). Group 4 - each participant individually performs exercises that shape their skills.

The basis of the game of handball is natural movements that help the players to develop harmoniously in all aspects, such as running, jumping, passing the ball, running, throwing. Loads have a positive effect on the development of all functional systems in the body. Under the influence of training, as well as in competitions, mental activity of participants improves, qualities such as speed, imagination, creative thinking and initiative develop. Handball can be a good tool for general

fitness. Handball is a necessary sport for a student of any specialty due to the development of physical qualities, at the same time, willpower, and tactical thinking by changing the direction, different types of running, jumping, and moving at maximum speed. is among the games.

Reminding of the importance of the result of the game and the need to win does not always give good results. Every athlete must have highly developed willpower. Courage, determination, simplicity and perseverance, initiative, discipline is the main willpower. These feelings are nurtured during training.

Preparation for the performance of specified tasks is the basis of the handball player's body capabilities and physical training. The level of such opportunities is clearly reflected in the activity of their supporting muscle system. For training-induced changes to be sustained, a player must be able to perform a specific task over a long period of time.

In the game of handball, methods are performed with and without the ball. Handball technique is a set of different special methods used in the game to achieve the goal. Handball technique is divided into field player technique and goalkeeper technique. Management techniques are divided into sections. Subsections consist of specific techniques performed in different ways - styles and methods of movement techniques. Outfield players and goalkeepers are made of them. The main mechanism of movement in methods and types is common, and differs only in details. The conditions for performing different methods make handball technique even more diverse. Handball technique can be divided into two major parts: "attack" and "defense technique". Attack techniques are divided into "movement" and "possession of the ball" methods, and defense techniques are divided into "movement" and "possession against the ball" methods. Each component contains game activities, which in turn are implemented in several ways. 1) the number of hand and foot movements when performing the technique (one or two); 2) the movement of the hand with the ball in relation to the position of the shoulder (up, side, bottom); 3) the movement of the ball transfer methods (swing, kick).

Acting as an attacker and a defender on the field and the method of deceptive actions are the basis of the game technique. The initial state - determines standing, preparation and movement. Standing high and low are different, the situation dictates which position to stand. In modern handball, standing in a high position (legs slightly bent), shoulder-width apart, body slightly bent forward, and arms are held in a bent position. The player who moves quickly and efficiently on the field will benefit the most.

It is a very important and complex part of training in the process of improving physical qualities. In addition to physical and technical preparation, the ability to use one's own abilities correctly and skillfully is of great importance in winning over the opponent's team. To improve the tactical skills of handball players, repetition of mastered and learned exercises many times is the main method (method) of education and training in tactics.

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The quality of knowledge, skills, and abilities of future economists about social media marketing through the design method

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Annotation: In today's digital age, social media has become an integral part of our daily lives, including the world of business and economics. As such, future economists need to have a solid understanding of social media marketing and its impact on the economy. One effective way to teach this subject is through project-based learning, which involves designing and implementing projects that allow students to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios. This literature review explores the effectiveness of project-based learning in teaching social media marketing to future economists, as well as the role of personal learning environments and social media in self-regulated learning. Additionally, this review examines the urban legends in education that suggest learners always know best, and how scaling up learning design can impact LMS behavior and performance. Finally, this review provides a comprehensive guide for educators on how to use social media for learning.

Keywords: social media marketing, project-based learning, personal learning environments, self-regulated learning, urban legends in education, scaling up learning design, LMS behavior, social media for learning.

Social media marketing has become an essential tool for businesses to reach their target audience and promote their products or services. The field of economics is no exception as it has seen a significant shift towards digital marketing in recent years. However, the education system has been slow to adapt to this change, and there is a need to incorporate social media marketing into the curriculum of economics programs. This literature review aims to explore the quality of knowledge, skills, and abilities of future economists about social media marketing through the design method.

Project-Based Learning: Project-based learning (PBL) is a teaching method that allows students to learn through hands-on experience. It involves the creation of

a project that requires students to apply their knowledge and skills to solve a real-world problem. PBL is an effective method for teaching social media marketing as it allows students to work on real projects and develop their skills in a practical setting. Personal Learning Environments: Personal learning environments (PLEs) are a way for students to take control of their learning by creating a customized learning environment that suits their needs and preferences. PLEs can be used to teach social media marketing by allowing students to access relevant resources and tools, collaborate with peers, and create their content. Self-Regulated Learning: Self-regulated learning (SRL) is a process where students take responsibility for their learning by setting goals, monitoring their progress, and adjusting their strategies as needed. SRL can be used to teach social media marketing by encouraging students to reflect on their learning, identify areas for improvement, and develop strategies to improve their skills. Urban Legends in Education: Urban legends are false stories that are widely believed to be true. In education, urban legends can be harmful as they can lead to ineffective teaching practices. One urban legend in social media marketing is that it is only useful for businesses with large budgets. However, this is not true as social media marketing can be effective for businesses of all sizes.

It is important to dispel these myths and teach students the truth about social media marketing. Scaling Up Learning Design: Scaling up learning design involves taking successful teaching practices and applying them on a larger scale. This can be done by creating online courses or using technology to reach a wider audience. Scaling up learning design can be used to teach social media marketing by creating online courses that are accessible to students around the world. MS Behavior: Learning management systems (LMS) are used to manage and deliver online courses. LMS behavior refers to the way students interact with the LMS and how it affects their learning. LMS behavior can be used to teach social media marketing by creating interactive courses that engage students and encourage them to participate in discussions and activities.

Social Media for Learning: social media can be used as a tool for learning by allowing students to connect with experts, access resources, and collaborate with

peers. Social media for learning can be used to teach social media marketing by allowing students to observe how businesses use social media to promote their products or services and by encouraging them to create their social media campaigns.

Conclusion: In conclusion, incorporating social media marketing into the curriculum of economics programs is essential for preparing future economists for the digital age. The design methods discussed in this literature review, including PBL, PLEs, SRL, dispelling urban legends, scaling up learning design, LMS behavior, and social media for learning, can be used to teach social media marketing effectively. By using these methods, educators can ensure that students have the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary to succeed in the field of economics.

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Development of individual work of students in the context of digitalization of education

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the issues based on the development of individual work of students in the context of digitalization of education. The need to modernize the structure of the educational process, including the independent work of students, is determined by the requirements of the digital economy and the modern information society, in which the process of digitalization of education takes one of the leading roles. The introduction of digital tools, the transition to a digital educational environment, the development and use of digital educational resources, the development of online education - all these are integral components of the modern educational system.

Keywords: digital technologies, education system, individual work, digitalization of education.

The development of digital technologies, social networks and instant messengers has entailed a change in social values and led to online identification of a person. A new type of student has emerged who independently determines their educational path. They are focused on personal development and strive to combine work and study. Accordingly, the education system, while modernizing, must adapt to the requirements of the digital economy and the education system. In this regard, student training should be carried out through digital technologies in a digital educational environment. At the same time, the implementation of educational standards for training students and masters of the latest generation assumes a significant strengthening of the role of independent work in the formation of professionally significant qualities of a specialist capable of being competitive in the modern service market. The position of the student and teacher in the new conditions for the implementation of educational programs is being revised. In the requirements for the conditions for the implementation of bachelor's and master's degree educational

programs, special attention is paid to the digital educational environment, which should provide not only the master's access to electronic educational resources, but also ensure effective interaction of all participants in the educational process, including the use of network technologies at all stages of the educational process.

The revision of training in favor of digital educational technologies takes the process of organizing independent work of students and undergraduates to a new level. Not only the method of communication changes, but also the methods, forms, means and technologies of its organization at all stages of independent work. One of the most important indicators of a person's activity during an activity is its independence. Students must set primary and intermediate goals, plan activities to achieve them, choose tasks and type of work, plan time, distribute available resources and funds, carry out systematic self-monitoring of the progress of tasks, and make timely adjustments to the work.

The processes of digital transformation of education affect all aspects of the organization of the educational process. At the same time, the concept of independent work is being transformed. Firstly, the emphasis is shifting towards increasing the share of independent work and its personalization. Secondly, the tools for its organization are changing significantly. The digital educational environment becomes the basis for its organization, digital educational resources act as an indispensable teaching tool, feedback and control over the progress and result of students' independent work also occurs through digital technologies. Thus, the digital trans-Bibliographic list formation of education has led us to change the role and essence of the concept of independent work, which is recognized as the most effective means of developing abilities for self-education and self-realization in the conditions of the modern information society, the predominant type of activity in the digital educational environment.

N.B.Strekalova notes that in the structure of independent work in the context of the digital transformation of education, the need for an information technology component reflects the mandatory use of modern information processing tools and network collaboration in the digital educational environment in independent work.

B.P. Esipov determines that independent work as a type of activity that “is carried out without the direct participation of the teacher, but according to his instructions and at a time specially provided for this; at the same time, students consciously strive to achieve their goal, showing their efforts and expressing in one form or another the results of their mental and physical actions” [2].

In our opinion, the independent work of students in the context of the digital transformation of education is determined by the possibilities of using digital technologies, where network technologies and services, digital educational resources, mobile applications and open online courses are highlighted, as well as the main areas of independent work: independent work within academic disciplines, research work and project activities.

Thus, we can conclude that, taking into account the multicomponent structure of independent work and the change in its essence in the context of the digital transformation of education, independent work can be considered as a purposeful self-organized information and research activity of students, carried out using digital technologies under the influence of pedagogical management and self-government as mechanisms ensuring its quality.

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Unleashing student professional competence through the power of mobile technologies

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ABSTRACT

In the modern paradigm of higher education, lexical competence is the basis for the formation of professional and communicative competence of a future specialist. One of the ways to develop lexical competence can be mobile technologies. An analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature has shown that this issue has been little studied. The article deals with the issues based on unleashing Student Professional Competence through the Power of Mobile Technologies.

Keywords: mobile technologies, professional process, young professionals, methodology.

In the era of globalization and technical innovation, the rapid development of information technology, the emergence and widespread distribution of mobile devices have led to significant changes in the system of teaching foreign languages (hereinafter referred to as FL). Since candidates who speak a foreign language and are able to effectively use it in the field of professional communication have a clear advantage in the labor market, the problem of ensuring the quality of professional foreign language training of future non-linguistic specialists comes to the fore.

To ensure competitiveness in the labor market, the modern higher education system is faced with the task of training specialists, which is based on the formation of competencies that allow graduates to become highly cultural IT specialists and easily navigate various areas of social and professional life.

In modern conditions, students are faced with the task of mastering business communication based on professional vocabulary. Such qualification requirements for training are conditioned by the need to create conditions for the formation of a high level of professional and communicative competence among future specialists, which is based on the possession of foreign language professional vocabulary.

Mobile learning (m-learning) is the transfer and receipt of educational information and reference materials using compact portable devices with mobile applications and Internet access and always available wireless technologies to any portable mobile device in order to form aspects of foreign language skills [1].

However, according to J. Kelly, the main goal of mobile learning is not the use of convenient mobile devices that allow students to receive or provide educational information in any format at anytime, anywhere, but to create innovative mobile learning materials that would make the learning process more visual and interesting for the student [1]. Thus, mobile learning of a foreign language is a form of organizing the learning and control process that involves mastering certain knowledge, improving language skills, and developing speech skills, taking into account the specifics of students' future professional activities [2]. In various sources you can find a description of the forms and methods of introducing mobile technologies into the educational process of open education:

1. Providing access to the Internet: to sites containing educational material; to specialized sites that provide electronic training courses, test and practical tasks, as well as additional training materials (graphic files, sound and video files).
2. Exchange of e-mails for educational purposes and instant messages through specialized programs.
3. A mobile phone is used as a means to play audio, text, graphic and video files that contain educational information.
4. The use of special programs on mobile phone platforms that can view and edit office program files MSWord, PowerPoint and Excel. Files with training information can be viewed in an adapted format, tailored specifically for the phone screen.
5. Organization of training using adapted electronic textbooks, training courses and various files that contain training information. For example, students are provided with an application to download to their mobile phone, which contains tests on a specific subject and electronic textbooks or lecture texts designed for their successful completion [2].

Using mobile technologies in the process of traditional learning includes providing students with access to sources of educational information contained in online courses using the educational portal of a training organization, which is adapted for mobile devices. These resources can be used for students' independent work in preparation for participation in seminars and debates, completing group projects, coursework, as well as various testing: self-testing, intermediate and final testing [1]. Another benefit is the ability for students to receive notifications, reminders, and checkpoint results on their mobile devices. In the process of face-to-face training, the capabilities of mobile devices can be used to carry out short testing at the end of the lesson, record important information (using an audio recording or a camera), and timely access to reference and educational materials during the lesson. Mobile devices can also be used to conduct practical classes without a computer lab. The introduction of mobile technologies in order to support the educational process helps improve the quality of education, the attractiveness of the educational services provided and increase the motivation to learn for students. Learning becomes timely, sufficient and personalized. Based on the above, we can conclude that today research related to the methods and methods of using mobile technologies is timely, promising and relevant.

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Modern Learning System in education and advantages of studying in non-state institutions

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Abstract: Modern learning systems have been spread all over the world, which is useful and easy for humans. In this era, there is an increased usage of the internet in educational applications; this could mean that human beings will increasingly make use of technology within open and flexible learning systems. It plays an important role in enhancing and developing our learning system. Intended outcomes as well as results of using modern techniques for teacher professional development need to be explored. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare them for the age of Modern Technology.

Key words; students and teachers to visualize 3D models, The principles of adult learning, communication through collaboration, What are Global Skills?,

The nation, people, nature, villages, towns or countries keep their inheritance and inherits to future generation that is the process that is unstoppable or that never ends. Learning the culture its rules, traditions are live styles will open the doors to improvement which cannot be changed. As result you can adopt the culture or new paces without any problems. Your view point or knowledge of cultural peculiarities and differences will make you idol person or the person who can survive in each part of the world, if she or she is chosen be sent to overseas. Books give opportunity to students and teachers to visualize 3D models in the real environment, in real time, and at scale. Many people believe that methods and techniques that are widely used in a country such as America and Britain give the chance to adopt the language better and success of students depend on it. What is the current pedagogy in education in the GB and what are the innovative methods employed to support it? There has been a huge change in, for example how reading and literature is taught. Reading, when I was at university was taught mainly through having access to read books and been immersed in a rich culture of text and opportunities for accessing stories, poetry, letters, biographies, instructions and other forms of the written words. The

prevalence of social media and the internet as a whole have changed the way people learn languages for the better. Learning materials should be seen as a dynamic part of the learning process and not just something given out to learners. The principles of adult learning should be incorporated into their development and use, so that they are practical, oriented and relevant to the learners' situation and learning needs. A variety of learning materials should be used to encourage learning for knowledge, attitudes and skills. Find A comfortable, peaceful place for quiet study. You need somewhere where you can focus 180%. Last but not least, learn English with LOVE. What Are Global Skills. There are various frameworks of global skills that are presented by, amongst others, UNESCO, OECD, and various ministries of education worldwide. It is widely recognised that Global Skills can and should be taught and assessed in educational settings. With ELT having an emphasis on communication through collaboration, the language classroom is a natural habitat for developing such skills. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) are ideal contexts for Global Skills, but there is scope for all language teachers to bring Global Skills to their classes – whatever the level, age group, or context. Global skills in ELT Global Skills can be summarized using five skills-clusters: communication and collaboration, creativity and critical thinking, intercultural competence and citizenship, emotional self-regulation and wellbeing, digital literacies. These five clusters support each other and can easily be integrated into the language classroom. Each of them has a set of learner profiles: Cluster 1: Communication and Collaboration Cluster 2: Creativity and Critical Thinking Cluster 3: Intercultural Competence and Citizenship Cluster 4: Emotional Self-Regulation and Wellbeing Cluster 5: Digital Literacies.

Now we act as a dialogic partner, as a filter, as a stock taker, as an editor, as a model. We use the knowledge of courses offered by the Oxford Teachers Academy, Department for Continuing Education, University of Oxford, and Oxford, United Kingdom of Great Britain. These were very beneficial as we share trainings knowledge that we gained in the live lessons with international teachers. We started

to work as a model, as an expert and as a supporting teacher. Now we can create the workshops depending on the needs and demands. What are Global Skills? There are various frameworks of global skills that are presented by, amongst others, UNESCO, OECD, and various ministries of education worldwide. It is widely recognised that Global Skills can and should be taught and assessed in educational settings. With ELT having an emphasis on communication through collaboration, the language classroom is a natural habitat for developing such skills. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) are ideal contexts for Global Skills, but there is scope for all language teachers to bring Global Skills to their classes – whatever the level, age group, or context.

Global skills in ELT

Global Skills can be summarised using five skills-clusters:

- communication and collaboration
- creativity and critical thinking
- intercultural competence and citizenship
- emotional self-regulation and wellbeing
- digital literacies.

These five clusters support each other and can easily be integrated into the language classroom. Each of them has a set of learner profiles:

Cluster 1: Communication and Collaboration

LEARNER PROFILE

Learners with **communication and collaboration** skills can:

- communicate effectively, appropriately, and sensitively with others in a range of contexts
- communicate effectively across diverse communication modes—written, spoken, or digital
- show empathy with others and understand a range of alternative perspectives
- collaborate by sharing their skills and supporting others
- collaborate through learning from others.

Cluster 2: Creativity and Critical Thinking

LEARNER PROFILE

Learners with **creativity and critical thinking** skills can:

- think flexibly to generate new ideas and solutions
- express themselves in creative ways through a range of language and media
- objectively analyse and evaluate material or information
- present coherent arguments about the source, reliability, and accuracy of information
- reach reasoned conclusions based on facts.

Cluster 3: intercultural competence and citizenship

LEARNER PROFILE

Learners with **intercultural competence and citizenship** skills can:

- demonstrate openness and curiosity about their own and diverse cultures
- communicate respectfully and appropriately with interaction partners from diverse cultural backgrounds
- understand and appreciate their own (multi)cultural identities
- demonstrate an awareness of their roles, responsibilities, and potential for action as citizens within society
- understand their local and global roles with regard to international issues, such as environmental issues and sustainable living practices.

In the next stage we work with aged teachers, the areas to be improved could be usage of modern teaching technologies, online teaching. We can start to help them by showing the usage of tools, helping to create worksheets, we advise to use teaching techniques that work better, answer their questions on programs that work best with digital tools in classrooms. Now we act as a dialogic partner, as a filter, as a stock taker, as an editor, as a model. We use the knowledge of courses offered by

the Oxford Teachers Academy, Department for Continuing Education, University of Oxford, and Oxford, United Kingdom of Great Britain. These were very beneficial as we share trainings knowledge that we gained in the live lessons with international teachers. We started to work as a model, as an expert and as a supporting teacher. Now we can create the workshops depending on the needs and demands. Currently, we are creating online class worksheets; our experience on needs of students will improve the quality of the worksheets. Because during the previous training teachers shared their ideas on needs and demands of students. Now, we can create something useful, effective; act a sounding board to help teachers. We came to conclusion that we can support others; we became someone who can help to improve the teaching process, as we are experimenting various methods. Our stocktaking methods part of action learning sets (TSA- teacher support activity) turned out to be very efficient, as we received positive feedbacks after the usages of technology and techniques that we recommended to use.

CONCLUSION, programmed instruction is a research-based system which helps learners work successfully. The learning material may be a textbook or teaching machine or computer. The medium presents the material in a logical and tested sequence. The text is in small steps or larger chunks. After each step, learners are given a question to test their comprehension. Then immediately the correct answer is shown. This means the learners at all stages make responses, and given immediate knowledge of results. Learning from the context (English material that come from GB or America) is also one of the best ways to adopt the language. You will have the chance to see real and modern usage of the language. It means that you adopt the language better than just learning them from word lists that are provided. Using them in your speech in Life and in the real cases will Boost the vocabulary. For these reasons, to meet the international standards students use their Language in English speaking countries visiting or making friend from the countries where English is spoken as mother tongue, their communicating skills will improve and their can adopt the foreign words, items, peculiarities that do not exist in their country. The most Essential aspect of learning a language is loving in it living in it, using it to a

nonstop base, if the person stops using the language that he she learnt for while than they will forget the words or grammar structure that they learn , it means they have to learn the structures and words again from the beginning. According to statistics of Oxford university and findings of Harvard university child is born and uses the language by imitating listening its usage by the adults. So, he or she use it as a mother tongue. A child that is Russian but born in America can use the language of America with correct pronunciation and grammar rule. He or she may have a lot of mistakes in Russian or in other language that he uses later on. The place that we are born will and live in childhood will be Golden manuscripts in the brain in mind and pronunciations. For these reasons parents try to give their children to English schools. However, if it is not used in a family or with the children surrounded by the efficiency will be less accepted.

The nation, people, nature, villages, towns or countries keep their inheritance and inherits to future generation that is the process that is unstoppable or that never ends. Learning the culture its rules, traditions are live styles will open the doors to improvement which cannot be changed. As result you can adopt the culture or new paces without any problems.

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PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCE**The main features of the semantic-cognitive approach to the notion of concept in linguistics****Dalieva Madina Khabibullaevna,**

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Abstract: We designate the approach to linguistic-cognitive research that we are developing as semantic-cognitive, emphasizing with this name the main direction of research - the study of the relationship between the semantics of language and the concept sphere of the people, the relationship between semantic processes and cognitive ones.

Keywords: linguistic-cognitive research, concept, semantic-cognitive, linguistic means, conceptual meanings.

Cognitive linguistics became possible after the theoretical postulates of psycholinguistics were formalized. It was psycholinguists who substantiated the existence of nonverbal thinking, the existence in the minds of people of a concept sphere consisting of quanta of knowledge - concepts, constantly changing and updating. It turned out that language signs are created by people to exchange important information, that is, for the most common and communicatively popular concepts, that language signs are only a dotted line in the space of conceptual meanings, that the concept sphere is much more voluminous and wider than the part of it that is designated by linguistic means. These theoretical achievements of psycholinguistics became the basis for the creation of the methodology of cognitive linguistics. The main position of this methodology is that through the study of the semantics of linguistic signs one can penetrate into the conceptual sphere of people, one can find out what was important for a particular people in different periods of its history, and what remained outside the field of vision, while for other people this turned out to be significant. Based on this methodological position, methods of cognitive linguistics were developed, which now make it possible to detect the characteristics of not only national, but also group thinking, and the entire diversity of individual author's concept spheres. The main postulates of the approach we are

developing are as follows. Human thinking is non-verbal; it is carried out using a universal subject code. People think in concepts encoded by units of this code and forming the basis of a universal subject code (Vygotsky 1982, Zhinkin 1958, 1982, 1998, Gorelov 1980, 2003, Gorelov, Sedov 1998). A concept is an affiliation of human consciousness, a global unit of mental activity. An ordered set of concepts in a person's mind forms his concept sphere. Language is one of the means of access to human consciousness, its conceptual sphere, to the content and structure of concepts as units of thinking. Through language one can cognize and explicate a significant part of the conceptual content of consciousness. Linguistic methods used to describe the lexical and grammatical semantics of language units become methods of lingue cognitive research. Cognitive linguistics studies the semantics of units that represent (objectify, verbalize, externalize) one or another concept in language. The study of the semantics of linguistic units that objectify concepts allows one to gain access to the content of concepts as mental units. The totality of meanings of linguistic units forms the semantic space of the language. Concept is a unit of the concept sphere; meaning is a unit of semantic space of language. Meaning is an element of linguistic consciousness, concept is cognitive ("general"). Concept and meaning are equally phenomena of a mental, cognitive nature. Meaning is part of a concept as a mental unit, fixed by a linguistic sign for the purpose of communication. A distinction is made between psycholinguistic meaning ("psychologically real", that is, in the entire scope of semantic features associated with a word in the mind of a native speaker; revealed mainly by experimental techniques) and "lexicographical" meaning (briefly formulated, reflected in explanatory dictionaries).

The concept, if it is named, includes psycholinguistic and lexicographic meaning as its component parts, but in terms of the volume of its content it remains immeasurably larger than both of the above-mentioned meanings. The concept does not necessarily have a connection with a word or other linguistic means of verbalization. A concept may or may not be verbalized by linguistic means. In the act of speech, the communicatively relevant part of the concept is verbalized. The

study of the semantics of linguistic units that verbalize a concept is the way to describe the verbalized part of the concept. The reasons for verbalization or lack of verbalization of a concept are purely communicative (communicative relevance of the concept). The presence or absence of verbalization of a concept does not affect the reality of its existence in consciousness as a unit of thinking. There are a large number of non-verbalized concepts in the mind. A significant part of the concepts of individual consciousness are not subject to verbalization at all. The presence of a large number of nominations for a particular concept indicates the nominative density (term by V.I. Karasik - 2002, p. 111) of this section of the language system, which reflects the relevance of the verbalized concept for the consciousness of the people. A concept can be verbalized in case of communicative necessity in various ways (lexical, phraseological, syntactic, etc.), by a whole complex of linguistic means, the systematization and semantic description of which makes it possible to identify cognitive features and cognitive classifiers that can be used to model the concept. The concept has a certain structure, which is not rigid, but is a necessary condition for the existence of the concept and its entry into the concept sphere. Concepts are internally organized according to the field principle and include a sensory image, information content and an interpretative field. The structure of the concept is formed by cognitive features of different ranks, which differ in the degree of brightness in the consciousness of their bearers and are ordered in the structure of the concept according to field characteristics. The national, social, group and individual specificity of the concept is observed. Concepts have national characteristics of content and structure; Endemic concepts are possible, lacunarity of the concept is possible.

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The role of reference materials in language teaching

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Annotation: Nowadays nobody can argue that there is a significant awareness arisen among individuals regarding potential implication of issues associated with the role of using reference materials in learning language. There are several situation and relevant solutions are available for dealing which will be elucidated in the following paragraphs.

Key words; reference materials, useful to learners, useful reference facility for learners, difficulties about producing reference materials

Introduction

Although many learners will have grammar books and reference materials available, their most convenient reference source will be the learning materials themselves. The information presented should be limited to that which is relevant to the stated objectives and written in a way, which is useful to learners. It should also make cross-reference to other unites in which the items are deal with. Most importantly, we can expect the materials to give information on functions notions, discourse, which learners would be less likely to find in grammars. The explanations may be in the mother tongue for those at the lower levels of language learning, however intermediate learners may be able to cope with language explanations, in this situation they are valuable examples of the authentic use of the language. Whatever language they are in, they must be simple and clear, and diagrams and illustrations may be helpful. References to the occurrences of the item in the passage of the materials may also help learners to understand the explanations and this also help them to work out meaning in the text. In addition, reference materials in vocabulary may be presented as a single glossary or separate lists may be supplied in each unit of the materials. A recapitulative list is very useful reference facility for learners, helping them to recover meanings for words who they have learnt but subsequently forgotten. Word lists in each unit are less important as a reference, but they are useful

as an aide-memoire of what has been covered. If word lists are able to utilize for reference purposes clearly, they must supply the word meaning in the other way. The most relevant method of doing this, once again, differ with the level of the target learner; beginners require either a translation into the mother tongue or visual clues, whilst more advanced learners may be able to cope with definitions in the target language. It is important that word meaning is related to the context of the occurrences of the word and so the glossary should refer to key occurrences. There are particular difficulties about producing reference materials for the spoken language. Learners will wish to find out how to pronounce individuals' words, what particular intonation actually sound like and what they mean in particular contexts, what the effects are of the elisions in the production of utterances and so on. The use only of written notations for these is not enough and the only satisfactory system is a combination of cassette recording and notation. In addition, instructions on learning pronunciation would be valuable for the self-instructing learner. This might consist of a brief and simple introduction to concepts such as phoneme and syllable, intonation and rhythm and their effects on meaning and discourse.

Conclusion

To conclude, there are several reference materials, which may help to motivate the learner to use the materials, and they contribute towards the maintenance of general motivation to learn the target language. These requirements are likely to be very difficult to meet for many individuals, but it is always possible to produce

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